
Creating an Inclusive Schools: A Conceptual Framework

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ABSTRACT

Inclusive education is a new approach to the education of children with disabilities and learning difficulties with the normal one within the same roof. It brings together all students in a classroom and community, regardless of their strengths or weaknesses in any area, and seeks to maximize the potential of all students. The present study tries to identify the various points for creating an inclusive school. It comprises different features of inclusive education in the present scenario. This study highlighted legal provision for inclusive education such as Article 21A, Article 14 deals with Right to Equality, Right to Education (RTE) Act 2009, Right with Disabilities (RPWD) Act 2016. This study also mentioned the needs and necessity of inclusive school. Section five of this study includes various essential points as aptly responsible for creating an inclusive institutions namely each school an inclusive school, adequate staff, identification of special needs children, assessments of special needs children, establishing school philosophy, enrolment drive, provisions of incentives, and heterogeneous setting, Last section deals with various essential points like adequate staff, identification of special needs children, assessments of special needs children, establishing school philosophy, enrolment drive, provisions of incentives, and heterogeneous setting as aptly responsible for creating inclusive school.

Introduction:

Everyone has the right to education, according to the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Munongi, 2022). In particular, the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization held an international conference in Salamanca, Spain, in 1994 with the title "The International Conference on Education for People with Special Needs: Access and Quality." This conference produced the 1994 framework and statement on inclusive education. Twenty-five international organizations and 92 nations signed this declaration. This statement's primary goals were to advance and create an inclusive educational system on a worldwide scale. Inclusive education is an innovative movement that many nations aim to adopt as a original idea and work toward implementing as an application of scientific advancements, the education of individuals with disabilities, and in compliance with the applicable international conventions. Inclusion is referred to as a whole school approach. Inclusive education brings all students in one platform or classroom and community regardless of their strength and weakness in any area. Inclusive school is a platform where everyone belongs, is acknowledged, supports and is supported by his or her peers and other members of the school community in the course of having his or her educational needs met (Stainback and Stainback, 1992). It aims to provide a favorable condition for achieving equal opportunity and full participation for all thus bringing children with special needs well the preview of mainstreaming education. In today's school systems do not respond to the needs of children with diverse abilities. The present schools entertain the average student's needs and desires. Though, in some schools needs with special children are directly integrated in the heterogeneous setting of the regular classroom. But in some other schools special needs children are placed part-time in the heterogeneous setting of the regular classroom and part-time in the homogenous group in the resource room. In simple words, it means that all students with or without disability learn together.

So there is a vital need for reforms to the school system. Above all, support for improving school systems to meet various students' needs must join together and recognize the principle that 'good schools are good schools for all students' and then act on that principle. The following factors contribute to creating and maintaining a successful inclusive school.

❖ Characteristics of Inclusive Education

Certain characteristics of inclusive education can be mentioned as:

1. The original ground of inclusion is that all children can learn and belong to the mainstream of school and community life.

2. Inclusion describes the process by which a school attempts to cater to all pupils, with and without disability, by reconsidering its curricular organization and provision.
3. Inclusive education brings all students together in one classroom and community, regardless of their strengths or weaknesses in any area and seeks to maximize the potential of all students.
4. Inclusive education is a process of overcoming barriers and enabling all students to learn together. All students will participate effectively within general school systems.
5. Inclusion is an educational approach and philosophy that provides students with community membership and greater opportunities for academic and social achievement.

Inclusion is about making sure that each and every student feels welcome and those unique needs and learning styles are attended to and valued (Mquadi, 1999; Pal et al 2014).

1. What are the legal protections and rights for people with disabilities in the education system?
2. Why inclusive education concept has emerged in present education scenario?
3. What are strategic plan for creating inclusive school?

❖ **Objectives:**The present study entails the following objectives:

1. To make a knowledge and an understanding about inclusive education.

❖ **Review of this study;**

Panda,A. (2024) examined critical examination of NEP 2020's special education and differently-abled student policies strengthens the need for a uniform approach to guarantee inclusion in inclusive education. Furthermore, to ensure an enlightened shift in schooling, it is critical to preserve homogeneity across several phases.

Buenano-Barreno, 2024 expressed that the goal of inclusive education is to guarantee that every student has access to education by accommodating their various needs, including those of those with special needs.

.Chanda, P. (2023) showed a study on Legal Policies and Provisions to Provide Equal Opportunities in Education to Special Needs gives a detailed view on the rights of differently abled students in the

education context and their legal provisions. The education for all concept is ensuring through differently abled students through various methods and highlighting the inclusivity of every child.

Ghosh et al., 2022 told that the goal of inclusive learning settings is to include every student in the educational process, notwithstanding their unique characteristics. In light of their various requirements and learning preferences, they seek to guarantee that every student has access to fair educational opportunities that respect diversity and encourage unrestricted involvement.

Van Mieghem et al., (2018) demonstrated that the main focus of inclusive school development has been on preparing teachers to work with kids who have special educational needs (SEN) in an inclusive classroom.

Merzon et al., (2022) mentioned that Teachers and students can benefit greatly from using digital educational technology to build technical abilities, particularly in the area of inclusive education.

❖ **Legal provision for inclusive education:**

According to Article 21A, all children, including those with disabilities, between the ages of 6 -14 years age group, have the fundamental right to an education. Article 14 deals with right to equality, and the Right to Education (RTE) Act of 2009 and the Right of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act of 2016 have both been incorporated into our constitution. By encouraging equitable access to highquality education for all, regardless of background or ability, NEP 2020 lays a significant emphasis on inclusive education. The strategy aims to reduce inequalities for socioeconomically disadvantaged groups (SEMGs), including girls, children with impairments, and marginalized communities. The National Education Plan 2020 talks about inclusive education, which aims to nurture the economically backward classes, promote equality and diversity, and incorporate special teaching strategies in teachers, needs-based sensitivity and ensure that everyone can participate and benefit from education.

❖ **Statement of the Problems:** Given the aforementioned critiques, the study's title should be rephrased as "**Creating an Inclusive Schools: A Conceptual Framework.**"

❖ **Research questions;**

2. To highlight the features of inclusive education in the present scenario;
3. To make an awareness about the principles as well as procedures for creating an inclusive education in schools;
4. To identify the general viable points for creating inclusive schools.

❖ **Need and Necessity of inclusive school**

Approximately 8 million children in India are not in school, according to MHRD 2009 estimates. Many of these children are disenfranchised due to factors including caste, gender, poverty, and disability. **To meet the many learning needs in a general learning environment, inclusive schools are needed. Inclusive schools are needed to improve social and academic skills, foster empathy and diversity, and provide a better society for all.** *It is necessary to create a barrier-free school environment for all, where everyone, regardless of race, religion, caste, gender, or financial status, can have equal opportunities. A common school environment is needed for everyone to be admitted, to be trained, to have access to opportunities, and to develop according to their own intelligence. Inclusive school helps to Improve Social & Emotional Development, increase academic Outcomes, Develop essential life skills, increase self-esteem & confidence of the students. This school fosters a Inclusive Society, reduces discrimination among students, build stronger communities, prepare diverse Workforce.* The following diagram illustrates the need for inclusive education for the diagram point of view.

- **Educational factors:** All children have the chance to learn from one another and acquire the values, attitudes, and skills required for the current communities through inclusive education.
- **Sociological Factors:** Schools ought to encourage broader social acceptance, cooperation, respect, acceptance, and support among kids as well as societal values. Education that is inclusive fosters the social value of equality. It strengthens bonds between peer groups, teaches students to respect teachers, lessens prejudice, and gets them ready for life in the mainstream through inclusive education.
- **Legal Provisions:** According to many sections and articles of the Indian constitution, all children, special needs or not, have the right to an education that fosters equality. Children with disabilities must, by policy, get their education in regular schools for as long as possible in India.

- **Humanitarian Perspective:** Programs for education should be made available so that children with disabilities can participate in, contribute to, and gain as much as possible from daily life. Both children with and without special needs have the capacity to achieve great success in their chosen careers and independent community living. To guarantee true equality of opportunity, inclusive education is the ideal environment.
- **International Pressure;** The 1989 V.U. Convention on the Rights of the Child lays forth children's rights, including the freedom from discrimination and the ability to express their opinions and desires.
- **Economic factors;** We have one million people with disabilities (disabilities, April 2003), which is projected to be 10% of India's total population. This group cannot be disregarded while making plans for education, employment, and development.

❖ **Essential principles for creating an inclusive school:**

1. Each School an Inclusive school: Every school will be an inclusive school where every child with special needs will receive education in his neighborhoods school. In order to provide the right to education to all students with special needs, every neighborhoods primary school should be an inclusive school. In this regard Administrators will take steps for the expansion of inclusive education facilities. The social-justice approach to educational planning and management will be followed in the spread of inclusive education. The thrust of social justice approach is: justice to all, and injustice to none.

2. Provision of adequate suitable staff: To create an Inclusive school, a sufficient number of regular trained teachers are required.. For creating an inclusive school, every school should have at least five teachers. An experienced teacher of the school should be provided proper training in the principle of inclusive education.

3. Identification of special needs children: Special needs children are identified by the teachers based on daily academic progress and failure in school related subjects. Identification is essential for creating an inclusive environment, obtaining appropriate aids and equipments for such children, better exposure to education, better psycho-social adjustment and better achievements of special needs children.

4. Assessment of special needs children: Assessment means the systematic process of gathering educationally relevant information about special needs children to enable the headmaster and the teachers to make proper infrastructure arrangement, classroom management and to take instructional decisions.

In School, teacher assesses the achievement, reading and writing ability of students over the year. Few cases medical assessment and psychological assessment are not possible due to unavailability of specialists in the locality and/or unwillingness of parents to take their children to district hospital for assessment purpose. In such cases teachers can rely on scientific/formal functional assessment procedures which provide authentic information about the child's academic success, failure, weaknesses and mistake.

❖ **Strategies plan for inclusivity:**

School inclusion model (SIM) has three main pillars –leadership, organizational justice and academic results (**Madsen and Mebokela,2005**). *According to this paradigm, establishing inclusive contexts requires strong leadership. It is required of school administrators to be able to establish an inclusive atmosphere. Additionally, Inter showed a degree of flexibility, adaptability, and appreciation for diversity. Emphasis on improving the economic status of socio-economically backward groups, giving importance to mother tongue or regional language in education, and providing education in mother tongue at least up to the fifth or sixth grade, and to develop human resources in the country by incorporating technology in the field of education*

❖ **Establishing a school philosophy**

A school philosophy has to be establishing for creating a quality inclusive school. It will be based on the democratic, egalitarian principles of inclusion, belonging, and provision of quality education to all children. A quality inclusive school focuses on the needs of ‘whole child’ not only on academic achievement. Relevant education will be provided to all children such as the academic, the social and emotional by which students can establish them in changing environment

Inclusive schools in different countries retain a philosophy such as the following:

1. Every child is welcome to the school.
2. Every child belongs to the school.
3. Quality education should be provided to children with special needs.
4. Every child can learn according to their ability.
5. Children with special needs are accepted as members of the school community
6. No child should be denied admission on the disability
7. Children with special needs should be educated in regular classrooms/schools
8. Education of special needs children is the responsibility of each and every teacher; and
9. The school should be supportive community

Each and every inclusive school has a certain philosophy which is a mission statement. The vision of inclusive schools is to bring all with disabled and without disabled students in a one heterogeneous platform. This will ensure their active participation and co- operation in making the school a community where everyone belongs, is accepted and respected, and is supported by others.

6. Enrolment drive and Measures for retention: Enrolment drive through parent contact programme, a community awareness programme can help to increase enrolment of special needs children, particularly girls and in rural areas. Measures should also be taken so that all special needs children enrolled in schools stay in and complete primary education. Thus the congenial conditions for integrating the children in a school to enshrine their right to education are the following;

a. Infrastructural development : Adequate arrangement of school building is to be provided to students adequate arrangement for hostel accommodation with additional care system is to be ensured sitting arrangement in the class room school be reorganized suitably including are circulated and lighted room library facilities should be provided to that students drinking water toilet facility will be well organized.

b. Appropriate curriculum: Curriculum should be holistic which includes literature, language, arts and craft, humanities, games, sports, culture and value to ensure all rounded development. Curriculum should be flexible and relevant. The curriculum can facilitate the development of more inclusive setting when it leaves room for the centre of learning or the individual teacher to make adaptations so that it makes better sense in the local context and for the individual learner. In order to attract and retain children from marginalized and excluded group's education should respond flexibly.

c. Trained teachers: Trained teacher can bring their attitudinal change of special need children. Training is necessary arrangements. Successfully implement relevant curriculum and to consider students with special need training is needed which invites for the inventiveness.

d. Community participation: Community involvement or participation can run inclusive education smoothly and to fulfill with disabled or without disabled children in a same setting. They adopt the concepts of inclusive education to their special children.

e. Family attachment: Apart from infrastructural development, suitable curriculum, trained teacher, family involvement is another way to successfully implement this system and provide effective and efficient delivery of quality education service. A special challenge is to get the families of the most marginalized students involved.

f. Advantageous Govt. Policy: Relevant and effective steps taken by the government can bring about change in the education system by assigning children's right to education for all can be fulfilled. Policy planner must be made aware of the importance and benefits of inclusive education. To help this process inclusion can be linked with the reform of education system as a whole. This system linked closely together with the goal of education all and could be adopted as a philosophy to guide the education for all national action plans.

F. Seminar and symposium: It brings attitudinal change and awareness among the stakeholders (Pal, 2014; Mondal et al, 2014). Research by Fuller, et al. (1999) has showed that to achieve academically children must attend school regularly. A study of village-based schools in Malawi found that students with higher rates of attendance had greater learning gains, and lower rates of repetition, a finding consistent with many other studies (Miske, D., et al., 1998).

7. Condition of incentive: Incentives should be provided to increase attendance in schools of special needs children. Incentives in the form of stipends, scholarships and financial assistance by governments or/ other bodies/organizations can reduce dropout rate.

8. Heterogeneous grouping: Heterogeneous setting should be created with regard to placement of children with special needs children in schools. In some schools special needs children are directly included in the heterogeneous setting of the regular classroom. In some other schools special needs children are placed part-time in the heterogeneous setting of the regular classroom and part-time in the homogenous group in the reserve room.

❖ **Conclusion:** All children now have access to education, regardless of their caste, religion, ability, or other traits, thanks to the Right to Education Act of 2009. To establish an inclusive society, an inclusive approach is necessary. We must establish a welcoming, learner-friendly, and supportive inclusive learning environment if we want all kids to love learning. In order to establish an inclusive school. In order to promote inclusivity, the School Inclusive Model (SIM) emphasizes leadership organization, justice, and school outcomes. SIM has shown promise in improving school climate, raising parent participation, and altering how educators and leaders view our diversity. The objectives of inclusive education are to ensure equal opportunities across the educational system, foster compassion and acceptance, and promote diversity as a core value.

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